

Supplemental Abbreviations. Complete list of abbreviations used in the manuscript, including gene symbols and their associated gene names.

Supplemental Figures. **SFigure 1** Hierarchical Clustering on the DeepVsLobar gene list differentiates Deep ICH (blue) and Lobar ICH (green) subjects. The subject clustering does not show separation by time, which was different between Deep ICH and Lobar ICH groups ($p = 0.041$). Expression normalized and presented on a -2.0 to +2.0 scale. **SFigure 2** Overlaps between contrast-significant genes and the Group-significant genes used to generate the DeepPerGene (A), LobarPerGene (B), and DeepVsLobar (C) lists. In each panel, the contrast-specific genes are on the left and the Group-specific genes are on the right; the overlaps between these circles generated the gene lists analyzed in this study. The numbers presented in parentheses under significance criteria represent the total genes significant. The numbers in the Venn Diagram represent the number of genes in each section (from left to right in each panel: unique to the contrast, common and further analyzed, and unique to Group). **SFigure 3** The top 100 most significant genes in the DeepPerGene list differentiate Deep ICH (blue) from VRFC (gray) subjects on hierarchical clustering. Expression normalized and presented on a -2.0 to +2.0 scale. **SFigure 4** The top 100 most significant genes in the LobarPerGene list differentiate Lobar ICH (green) from VRFC (gray) subjects on hierarchical clustering. Expression normalized and presented on a -2.0 to +2.0 scale. **SFigure 5** T Cell Receptor Signaling is predicted suppressed but with upregulated inflammatory outputs in the LobarPerGene list. CHUK, a component of IKK in the pathway, mediates activation of NF- κ B, thus upregulating downstream inflammatory outputs. **SFigure 6** The DeepVsLobar list differentiates Deep ICH (blue), Lobar ICH (green), and VRFC (gray) subjects on hierarchical clustering. Expression normalized and presented on a -2.0 to +2.0 scale. **SFigure 7** Deep ICH vs. Lobar ICH gene list (hereafter referred to as DeepVsLobar) involvement in relevant canonical pathways. Apoptotic, Cytokine, Growth Factor, and Immune classified pathways are noted. The 36 differentially expressed genes were present but not enriched in a total of 47 pathways. These represent pathways that may have differing activation, signaling, or roles in Deep and Lobar ICH, even in common pathways. Connections between Genes (light purple nodes) and Pathways (light green nodes) indicate involvement of that gene in the canonical pathway. Connections between Pathways and Classifications indicate IPA defined classifications of the pathways involvement in general biological functions. Red gene names indicate higher expression in Deep ICH than in Lobar ICH; blue names indicate higher expression in Lobar ICH than in Deep ICH. **SFigure 8** Network dendrogram for the DeepICHandVRFC network and the gene assignments for the 30 modules. The two modules significant for Deep ICH vs. VRFC (DC-LightGreen and DC-Grey60) are labeled with their p-value. **SFigure 9** BEX2 signaling in DC-Grey60 was predicted downregulated, though with a nonsignificant Z-score of -1.3. Downregulation of this pathway then upregulates the function Cell Death of Dopaminergic Neurons through BEX2. **SFigure 10** Network dendrogram for the LobarICHandVRFC network and the gene assignments for the 32 modules. The five modules significant for Lobar ICH vs. VRFC (LC-Black, LC-DarkGreen, LC-Grey60, LC-Pink, and LC-RoyalBlue) are labeled with their p-value. **SFigure 11** Amyloid Processing in LC-Pink was predicted activated. It encompasses molecular signaling in response to Amyloid plaque buildup that results in neuronal death. **SFigure 12** Overlap of Deep and Lobar ICH pathways. A total of 209 pathways were common between locations; 26 and 92 were unique to Deep ICH and Lobar ICH, respectively. Hereafter, "common" refers to pathways, functions, processes, and GO terms that are common between locations. **SFigure 13** Enrichment in cell-type specific gene lists for the sex specific per-gene lists. Purple shading represents $-\log_{10}(p \text{ value})$ where 1.3 corresponds to a p value of 0.05; higher $-\log_{10}(p \text{ value})$ corresponds to lower

(more significant) p value. Non-significant hypergeometric probabilities are displayed as white cells. *Cell-type specific list from Watkins et al.²⁴; **Cell-type specific list from Chtanova et al.²⁵ For more comprehensive coverage of T cell-specific genes, ST1 and ST2 from Chtanova et al. were used; no overlap with Watkins et al. Th and Tc lists were found.

Supplemental Manuscript. Detailed methods and additional discussion of the findings of this study.

Supplemental Tables. **STable 1** Per-Gene list membership and statistics for DeepPerGene (A), LobarPerGene (B), and DeepVsLobar (C). **STable 2** IPA Canonical Pathway significant pathways (as well as their statistics and gene involvement) for DeepPerGene (A), LobarPerGene (B), DC-Grey60 (C), DC-LightGreen (D), LC-DarkGreen (E), LC-Pink (F), LC-Black (G), LC-RoyalBlue (H), DC-Grey60 Hubs (I), LC-Pink Hubs (J), Male-DvC (K), Female-DvC (L), and Female-LvC (M). Z-score cells with no value represent pathways for which an activity pattern was unable to be calculated. **STable 3** IPA Disease and Function significant terms (as well as their statistics and gene involvement) for DeepPerGene (A), LobarPerGene (B), DC-Grey60 (C), DC-LightGreen (D), LC-DarkGreen (E), LC-Pink (F), LC-Grey60 (G), LC-Black (H), LC-RoyalBlue (I), DC-Grey60 Hubs (J), DC-LightGreen Hubs (K), LC-DarkGreen Hubs (L), LC-Pink Hubs (M), LC-Black Hubs (N), LC-RoyalBlue Hubs (O), Male-DvC (P), Female-DvC(Q), and Female-LvC (R). Z-score cells with no value represent biofunctions for which an activity pattern was unable to be calculated. **STable 4** Gene Ontology significant terms (as well as their statistics and gene involvement) for DeepPerGene (A), LobarPerGene (B), DC-Grey60 (C), DC-LightGreen (D), LC-DarkGreen (E), LC-Pink (F), LC-Grey60 (G), LC-Black (H), LC-RoyalBlue (I), LC-Black Hubs (J), LC-RoyalBlue Hubs (K), Female-DvC (L), Male-LvC (M), and Female-LvC (N). **STable 5** Results, statistics, and gene overlaps for Hypergeometric enrichment in cell-type specific lists for DeepPerGene (A), LobarPerGene (B), DeepVsLobar (C), DC-Grey60 (D), DC-LightGreen (E), LC-DarkGreen (F), LC-Pink (G), LC-Grey60 (H), LC-Black (I), LC-RoyalBlue (J), DC-Grey60 Hubs (K), DC-LightGreen Hubs (L), LC-DarkGreen Hubs (M), LC-Pink Hubs (N), LC-Grey60 Hubs (O), LC-Black Hubs (P), LC-RoyalBlue Hubs (Q), Male-DvC (R), Female-DvC (S), Male-LvC (T), and Female-LvC (U). Please note: T Cells and T Cell Receptors and Signaling lists are from Chtanova et al.²⁵ for better coverage of T Cell Specific genes. All other cell specific gene lists are from Watkins et al.²⁴ **STable 6** Full IPA Pathway (A), IPA Disease and Function (B), and Gene Ontology (C) results for the DeepVsLobar gene list. Though minimal enrichment was found due to a small number of significant genes, we include full biological results to show the functions and processes these genes are involved in. Z-score cells with no value represent pathways/biofunctions for which an activity pattern was unable to be calculated. **STable 7** WGCNA statistics for module associations with parameters for DeepICHandVRFC Network (A) and LobarICHandVRFC Network (B). **STable 8** Gene memberships for modules associated with Group for DeepICHandVRFC Network (A) and LobarICHandVRFC Network (B). **STable 9** Per-Gene list membership and statistics for Male-DvC (A), Female-DvC (B), Male-LvC (C), and Female-LvC (D).